

Synthesis of W-ZrC and W-Zr(CN) Cermets

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1 Introduction

ZrC-based refractory materials are commonly used for high-temperature applications such as in engine, cutting tools, aero space vehicles. It is because ZrC has high melting point (3,445 °C), high modulus (310~380GPa), and excellent solid-state stability and it resists thermochemical reaction [1-4]. But it is not so easy to sinter due to porosity and isolated phase, many researchers have been reported about it [ref. 4-5]. In order to obtain the ideal W-ZrC composite, the manufacture of submicron sized carbide was needed by another method without commercial carbide. Our group is well known for refractory materials. The size can be controlled by using oxide materials and also ideal distribution can be obtained from carbothermal reduction. Because we obtained solid solution phase, this is the same method as we approached [ref. 6-7]. Recently, we reported the enhanced segregation of WC from (Ti,W)C solid-solution when N₂ atmosphere was used during the sintering. The affinity between W and N₂ is not as good as that between ZrC and N₂. This phenomenon can be applied to W-carbide system. In this work, so many approaches were designed. And we investigated the phase transition during the synthesis.

2. Experimental procedure

The powder samples were prepared from ZrO₂, WO₃, C and WC as starting materials in order to synthesize W-ZrC and W-Zr(CN). The start materials were weighed 25g batch which was milled at 250 rpm for 20hrs by planetary mill and heat treated in range of 1300-1500 °C for 2 hrs, 1600 °C for 1 hr under vacuum. The powder after carbothermal reduction at 1500 °C for 2 hrs was hot

pressed and sintered in graphite crucible at 1900 °C for 1hr. X-ray powder diffraction analysis was carried out for phase identification. The sintered body and the reduction powder were observed using a Scanning electron microscope in the Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) mode. And some cluster model was proposed from VASP program.

3. Results

In order to form W-ZrC and W-Zr(CN), the reaction occurs as follows. The equation (1) shows carbothermal reduction process about W-ZrC.

The W-ZrC composite materials were synthesized via high-energy milling and carbothermal reduction. Also a variety of W-ZrC system was designed from thermodynamics concept. From equation (2), the carbonitriding was performed by the milled powder of ZrO₂-WO₃-C in N₂ atmosphere. According to Kang et al., it is reported about segregation of WC phase when the (Ti,W)C carbide was sintered in N₂ condition. [ref. 8] This idea was useful to prohibit the synthesis of (Zr,W)C. And it is possible to synthesize WC-Zr(CN) or W-Zr(CN).

Fig.1. The XRD results about W-70mol.% ZrC

In order to observation about synthesis, the influence of temperature in figure 1 shows that W-ZrC was clearly synthesized from 1500°C-2hrs and 1600°C-1hr compare to lower temperature. According to figure 1, it showed the possibility to get a good crystallinity by controlling both two factors (duration time and temperature).

Fig.2 (Zr,W)C formation energy at room temperature by calculation

The formation energy of (Zr,W)C was calculated at room temperature in Fig. 2. The red line is an ideal solution line and the other is a real solution line. There is no difference between real solution and ideal solution.

Fig.4 (Zr,W)C formation energy at 1700K by calculation

The calculation results at 1700K show the same tendency compare to room temperature. When the solid solution was formed by simulation, the point of inflection was not observed.

It implies that it is hard to make solid solution between WC and ZrC.

Fig.5 (Zr,W)C formation energy at 3000K by calculation

As increasing temperature, the real solution shows deviation behavior. But the phase stability about WC in ZrC and ZrC in WC is always reduced.

Fig.6 The Gibbs free energy of mixing

The Gibbs free energy of mixing shows the positive deviation in fig.6. And also the phase separation was not occurred.

Fig. 7 SEM and EDS results about W-ZrC

The powder was agglomerated after carbothermal reduction. Fig. 7 shows SEM and EDS data in W-ZrC. The bright field (a) is W matrix and ZrC is located in the dark filed (b). It is hard to distinguish the (Zr,W)C solid solution phase due to the interaction volume of SEM.

Fig.8 the XRD results about W-Zr(CN)

Fig.8 shows the XRD results about W-40vol.% Zr(CN). The powder of W-Zr(CN) was synthesized at 1500°C-2h. Some minority was confirmed by W_xC_{1-x} phase. It is also consistent with calculation results. N_2 was over occupied in C site. It indicates that W is hard to form (Zr,W)C. The affinity between W and N_2 is not as good as that between ZrC and N_2 .

4. Conclusions

W-ZrC and W-Zr(CN) were successfully synthesized from WO_3 -ZrO₂-C mixtures. (Zr,W)C solid solution phase was reported by some researchers. According to our calculation and experimental results, it is difficult to observe any evidence for solid solution phase. The phase stability about WC in ZrC and ZrC in WC is always reduced from the calculation.

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